

The emigration of Francophone sub-Saharan African scientists, 2009-11 and 2019-21

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Abstract

We investigated the amount of emigration from 20 sub-Saharan African Francophone countries by examining the affiliations in two three-year periods, 2009-11 and 2019-21, of researchers with papers in the Web of Science and with surnames characteristic of each of these countries. We also analysed them by the major scientific field in which they were working. The percentages of emigrants were highest in Mauritania, Senegal, and Djibouti, and lowest in Madagascar, Burkina Faso, Togo, and Cameroon. We found a reduction in the percentages emigrating to western Europe, and notably those going to France. However, there was a big increase in the percentages who had moved to other African countries, particularly to South Africa, and the Mediterranean countries. Most of these Francophone countries had low rates of female participation in research (12 had less than 20%); Madagascar performed well above the world average with 42%. However, when they went abroad, females fared much better than in Africa. Agricultural and medical researchers were the ones least likely to emigrate. Emigrating scientists maintained strong research links with their former home countries.

Introduction

This project began with a study of cancer research in Africa (Mutebi et al., 2022), and our realisation that the continent was not able to keep up with the need for more research as African countries moved through the cancer transition. In particular, there was a great lack of research into childhood cancer, which accounts for well over 15% of the total burden from cancer in Africa, compared with 1 to 2% in Europe. This is just one example of where African research appears to be inadequate to address its burden of disease.

If more research is to be undertaken, then there need to be scientists – both clinical and non-clinical – across all countries in Africa to do the work. However, it is evident that for aspiring researchers, the opportunities are often greater in Europe or North America, or perhaps in some Asian countries. They will have better facilities, a wider range of disciplines, and often better remuneration. For some countries the drivers may also be instability, insecurity and (political) conflict in their home countries. They will be part of the well-known "brain drain", which most African countries have found very difficult to curtail.

But does this exodus of researchers occur equally in all African countries? Are there some countries where it is less damaging to the pursuit of research within their borders? If so, what means are applied by governments, or available from the private sector, to keep promising researchers at home? Do some of the African researchers go instead to other African countries, and if so, are they instrumental in stimulating good research there? Do they maintain links with their home country and contribute to international collaboration with it? Which subject

areas are the most likely to help, or hinder, researchers to travel abroad? And most important, are there policies that have been successful in keeping researchers at home?

There is a modest literature on the African brain drain. In the current century, we have found some 36 items in the Web of Science (WoS © Clarivate Analytics) that describe and bemoan it, of which about half (19) were journal articles. These items originated from 19 countries, ten in Africa and five in Europe, showing that the problem is of wide concern. Data on flows of scientists were obtained from many different sources, but were inevitably incomplete (Collier et al., 2004; Capuano & Marfouk, 2013; Kaplan & Höppli, 2017). Capuano & Marfouk based their analysis on census data from OECD countries on immigrants at three educational levels compiled by Docquier et al., (2009). A similar methodology was used by Kaplan & Höppli, who concentrated primarily on Australia, Canada, New Zealand, the UK and the USA, the main destination countries for South Africans with a tertiary education. Many papers addressed the exodus of health care professionals (Schrecker & Labonte, 2004; Muula, 2005; Pillay, 2007; Bhargava & Docquier, 2008; Kalpeni et al., 2012; Kasper & Bajunirwe, 2012; Onu et al., 2021) and its negative effects on health in Africa. Some emigrants compensate their home countries with remittances (Schrecker & Labonte, 2004; Bredtmann et al., 2019; Usman et al., 2022) but these are often insufficient to cover the cost of their education and training. There was little discussion about the movements of physical scientists. Of course most of the emigrants from Africa were Black, but the loss of White clinical psychologists from South Africa was also noted (Pillay & Kramer, 2003). By “emigrants” we mean people whose names indicate that they, or their fathers, are now affiliated to a country other than the one that is characteristic of their surname.

In this paper, we have adopted a novel approach to chart the movements of African researchers, initially from 20 Francophone sub-Saharan countries, on the basis of their surnames. These countries are listed in Table 1. We selected them as two groups, but not all of them speak French as their first language. We interrogated the WoS to identify the names of researchers from each of the selected countries. We listed these surnames and went to some trouble to identify ones that were primarily characteristic of the individual country and nowhere else. They would only have represented a sample of the researchers from the country, but we expected that they would be a reasonably unbiased selection and so a representative one in terms of their current locations and subject areas. We examined the affiliation countries for researchers with these surnames during two periods of three years, 2009-11 and 2019-21, separated by ten years, in order to see if there was any change in movement patterns. The actual numbers of papers increased greatly between the two periods, so we have presented the results as percentages of the respective totals. They do not show the *scale* of the migration from Africa, only the changing distribution of samples of the scientists from recipient countries, and the proportion of those who stayed at home.

We also examined the sex, or gender, of researchers from these 20 countries in order to determine the percentage of females, and also the balance of the sexes in the different major fields, and any changes over the study period. We did this by an examination of their given names, most of which can determine the sex of their holders, although some can be held by both sexes. This might indicate whether the situation in each country was conducive to the employment of women, who in theory could comprise half of the potential cadre of researchers.

Finally, we wondered if African researchers who emigrated continued to maintain scientific links with their former home country. There is evidence (Lewison et al., 2022) that Indians who emigrate to Canada do so. For Africans who went abroad, we identified the numbers of

papers by individuals with surnames characteristic of a particular country who no longer had an affiliation there, but were co-authored with a scientist remaining in that country. We then compared this number with their total output to see if their former home country was over- or under-represented among their international papers, relative to its presence in world research.

Table 1. List of sub-Saharan African Francophone countries with their ISO2 codes, populations in 2015 (millions), and numbers of surnames that appeared to be unique following filtering by Origins and checking with forebears.io.

<i>North and West Africa</i>				<i>Central and East Africa</i>			
<i>Country</i>	<i>ISO2</i>	<i>Pop,</i>	<i>Names</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>ISO2</i>	<i>Pop,</i>	<i>Names</i>
Benin	BJ	9.4	572	Burundi	BI	8.7	60
Burkina Faso	BF	17.5	356	Cameroon	CM	20.5	2825
Chad	TD	11.8	13	Central African Rep.	CF	4.6	48
Côte d'Ivoire	CI	20.6	315	Comoros	KM	0.8	19
Guinea	GN	10.5	49	Dem Rep Congo	CD	69.6	793
Mali	ML	16.3	87	Djibouti	DJ	0.9	30
Mauritania	MR	3.6	87	Equatorial Guinea	GQ	0.7	3
Niger	NE	16.6	161	Gabon	GA	1.6	172
Senegal	SN	13.1	97	Madagascar	MG	21.9	736
Togo	TG	6.3	100	Republic of Congo	CG	4.2	391
N & W countries		126	1837	C & E countries		134	5077

Methodology

This analysis, dependent on surnames, was based on three sources of data and is shown diagrammatically in Figure 1. One was the Web of Science, which since 2008 has tagged all authors with the address of the institution with which they are affiliated. The second was an informative website, www.forebears.io. This lists the most frequently-occurring surnames for each country and for regions within them, and conversely, lists the countries in which any given surname (or given name) is most commonly found, with its incidence and frequency. For example, in Mali one of the surnames that we listed was *Dembele*. Forebears.io showed that this name was most commonly found in Mali, with an incidence of 614,628, and a frequency of 1:28. The country with the second highest incidence was Burkina Faso, at 46,248. Since this was less than 8% of the incidence in Mali, we inferred that this was primarily a Malian surname, and therefore that people with this name could be regarded as either having originated from that country, or having a father who did so.

The third data source was a proprietary database "Origins", which categorises surnames into one of some 200 countries or regions. Some of these are super-national, such as "West African Muslim", and some are sub-national, such as "South Africa: Xhosa" or "South Africa: Zulu". Within Africa, Origins can allocate a name to one of 29 individual countries (14 Anglophone, 11 Francophone (of which three are in North Africa), and four others), and four regional groups. Not every African country has particular surnames in the Origins database. We had previously used this database in order to categorise world lung cancer researchers by their likely country of origin in order to show migration patterns (Lewison et al., 2016).

The use of names as a method for inferring the ethnic distribution of populations has been applied since 2000 in a number of applications, mostly to evaluate the representativeness of users of different medical prognoses and treatments, engagement in the arts and the take up of

local authority services (Webber, 2007; Evans et al., 2010) The method is used principally in situations where it is not practical to retrospectively append onto customer or client files categorisations of ethnicity derived from respondents to survey questionnaires.

Figure 1 Methodology for treatment of African surnames (example: Mali)

Whilst the coding of individuals based on their names will not necessarily match the codes that they might have given when asked to specify their ethnicity, experience suggests that such errors, if they are errors, are random rather than systematic. In addition, the granularity of categories for which statistics can be generated is much finer when based on names than when based on self-completion questionnaires.

Where the results of the two methods differ it is often the case that survey responses are indicative of an individual's aspiration and how they want to be treated whilst names tend to be more reliable indicators of ancestral heritage, religion and culture. This is because the way a person represents his or her family name is seldom affected by migration whilst parents' choice of personal names for their children is most likely to be influenced by religious identification and by language. Women often adopt their husband's name on marriage. This affects analysis to the extent that women marry men of different ethnic heritage in which case we identify instances where the heritage of their first name is inconsistent with that of their family name. One imagines that the behaviour of women married to husbands of a different ethnic background will itself differ from that of women marrying within their own heritage. Any bias caused by the adoption of a different name after marriage is, as far as we can tell, random rather than systematic.

The Origins database consists of a file of some 1.3 million personal names and some 4.0 million family names based on an examination of the records of 1.1 billion adults living in 26 countries. The database was created using data files from the period 2005 to 2022. Each name is associated with one of 250 ethnic categories which are then consolidated into 49 groupings. Typically, some 99% of the world's adults have names where at least either the personal name or the family name is recognised in the Origins database. Coverage does vary from country to country, with sub-Saharan Africa and South East Asia being two regions where, because of their large number of comparatively low frequency names, the overall hit rate is lower. This is why for this analysis we have felt the need to supplement the Origins database with information from Forebears.io. On the other hand, data from this project allowed us to improve the geographical coverage of Origins in Francophone sub-Saharan Africa, see Figure 1.

Given the arbitrary way in which Africa was divided into colonies and hence independent states, the geographical distribution of its common personal and family names matches territorial boundaries less well than it does in Europe. There are for example a small number of high frequency names, both personal and family, which are common throughout sub-Saharan Africa and are therefore less reliable as indicators of heritage at a country level. Most of these names are Muslim names. In these circumstances the algorithm Origins uses to classify adults with these family names relies to a greater extent than in other situations of the Origins category of their personal name. By contrast other than in South Africa and parts of East Africa it is more common for names common in one African country to be shared with immediate neighbours than with citizens of European or Asian heritage. In other words, the use of names is a very reliable method for inferring Black African ancestry even if it does not necessarily manage so well to classify names at an individual country level.

For each of the 20 Francophone sub-Saharan African countries listed in Table 1, we first used the WoS to generate a set of papers (articles and reviews only) in all fields of science and for the years 2009-21. Their details were downloaded by HS to a series of Excel files, and the address column was parsed to isolate the names of authors affiliated to an institution in that country. A macro (written by PR) was then used to list the surnames of these authors in

descending order of frequency. This exercise was repeated, first for the ten north-western sub-Saharan Francophone countries, and second for the ten in central and east Africa. Next, we visited Forebears.io to identify the most common surnames for each of the countries. The list could be up to 1000 names long, but for a few countries many fewer names were listed. These names were then added to those generated from the WoS, and duplicates removed. The composite lists of surnames for each country were then combined and those names identified that only occurred in a single country.

We then processed these lists with Origins in order to remove any names that were from outwith Africa, or that were characterised as coming from a country different from the one from which they came according to the WoS. Next, the WoS was searched for papers (again, articles and reviews only) for two three-year periods, 2009-11 and 2019-21, with an author with a surname from each of the lists in turn. Care was taken to remove any accents on the names, as the WoS does not record them. Details of the papers were again downloaded to Excel files and three sets of data were retained: the address column, the publication year column, and the WoS category column. We omitted the few papers that did not have an address. The individual papers were then numbered sequentially so that in the subsequent analysis each paper could be identified by its WoS category and by time period, "First" or "Second".

A special macro, again written by PR, was then applied to the set of paper details. It identified the full name of the author, their country of affiliation, the publication year, and the paper index number. To this list, we added the ISO2 code of the affiliation country and its continent (for each selected country, this was changed from AFR (Africa) to OWN). The other continents were: ASI = Asia, EEU = Eastern Europe, EUR = Western Europe, LAC = Latin America and Caribbean, NAM = North America (Canada + USA), OCE = Oceania.

The author names were copied to a new column, and their given names and/or initials truncated to a single initial. The file of papers was then sorted, first by affiliation country, second by time period, and third by author name and initial. A new column was then added, showing whether each name (*e.g.*, *Dembele, B*) was unique within each country and time period (coded "1"), or not (coded "0") Although very few researchers with given names with the same initial would have been amalgamated, this was a simple system for the identification of almost all of them. The file was then sorted once more, by country and author name and initial, and the papers marked "1" or "0" on the basis of the authors' names, as before. This generated slightly fewer unique names, as an author from a country in both periods was only counted once.

However, it soon became apparent that some of the leading surnames from individual countries looked as if they might not be primarily from that country. So we used Forebears.io again to check the country (or countries) where these names were most abundant. This check revealed that some surnames were primarily found in countries other than the one of immediate interest, or that they were often from other countries as well. Our criterion for acceptance of a name being primarily from the country of interest was that it should be at least ten times more frequent there than in the second country. If it failed the test, we then checked to see if there were individuals with that surname in our file who appeared to work in other countries listed by Forebears.io. If so, or if the primary source country for the surname was not the country of interest, then we removed all papers in the "Results" sheet for that surname. In effect, this surname was not an autochthonous one. Application of this checking procedure for a few countries, such as Chad, Mauretania, Niger, and Senegal led to the removal of many papers so the remaining names may not be representative and the results may be less reliable. However,

most of these Francophone countries were found to have researchers many of whose surnames were distinctive of the country with which our methodology had associated them, see Table 1.

As we wished to see whether the African "brain drain" affected researchers in some subject areas more than others, we used the "WoS Categories" data in column BI of the downloaded paper details, which had been copied across to our country data files, to show the major fields in which the named researchers were working. Many papers had been allocated to more than one WoS category; for these we just took the first, and then combined many individual WoS categories into 13 major fields, see Table 2. Each paper with an author name from a selected country could then be allocated to a major field, and by use of its index number, we were then able to annotate the Results sheet with the major field for each named researcher and paper. A pivot table, with only those papers where the named researcher was unique, could then be constructed, showing the numbers of researchers in each of the 13 major fields and each of the eight continental areas (OWN and seven others). We then multiplied the number of papers in each cell by the country's population (in millions) and divided by the total number of individual named researchers. We then combined the results for the two sets of Francophone countries, north and west, and east and central. This allowed us to see in which major fields the "brain drain" was taking place, and to which continents the two sets of African Francophone researchers had gone who were working in each field.

Table 2. Thirteen major fields in which African Francophone researchers worked.

<i>Code</i>	<i>Subject areas</i>	<i>Code</i>	<i>Subject areas</i>
AGRI	Agriculture; fisheries, food, forestry	MATE	Materials science; metallurgy
BIOL	Biology; biotechnology, genetics	MATH	Mathematics; statistics
CHEM	Chemistry; polymer science	MEDI	Medicine; anatomy, public health
ENGR	Engineering; imaging, telecoms	MULT	Multidisciplinary sciences
GEOG	Geography; environmental sci.	PHYS	Physics; astronomy
HUMA	Humanities; art, literature	SOCI	Social sciences; psychology
INFO	Information science; computer sci.		

For the determination of the sex, or gender, of the researchers in each of the 20 countries, we used four sources of data that can allocate it on the basis of given names. From an earlier study (Lewison et al., 2022) we developed a thesaurus of over 70,000 given names where sex was assigned if at least 75% of occurrences were of one sex. Since the coverage of African given names was not high, we also used the website Gender API (<https://gender-api.com>), which can take account of the country of the bearer of the name, and gives the frequency of occurrence and the sex ratio. The third data source was the Origins database, which can also assign sex to given names, especially if their ethnic or national origin is known. These three sources can sex long lists of given names. A potential fourth source, Forebears.io, can also sex given names individually, and it has the useful feature that it shows the ratio for the leading individual countries. For example, the given name *Kasso* in Benin is 83% male, but in Côte d'Ivoire it is 69% female. However, it is tedious to use this source as it only improves the coverage slightly (from 83% to 85%), and a better option is to sex individuals with more than one given name whose first cannot be reliably sexed but whose second (or third) name can be.

Our final analysis was designed to answer the question of whether those African researchers who went abroad stimulated scientific cooperation between their original home or heritage country and their new one. For each selected country, we first created a list of researchers

(surname + one initial) whose affiliations in our database were outwith their OWN country, and removed any who also published from there. We then searched the WoS for papers in the years 2009-11 and 2019-21 with one (or more) of these authors, and identified the papers with an address in their heritage country. This percentage was then compared with the heritage country's presence in world research during those years. For example, there were 519 different names of Senegalese researchers in our list who had emigrated, and collectively they wrote 3265 WoS papers in the six years. Of these papers, 43 had an address in Senegal, or 1.32%. This compares with the Senegalese presence of 0.0287% in world research in these years, and indicates that these authors were indeed maintaining strong links with their heritage country, by a factor of more than 45 compared with the null hypothesis. We carried out this analysis for five countries whose presence exceeded 0.02% of the world research total, and also for three where it was less than 0.003%.

Results

The two sets of Francophone countries are very different. Those in the north and west are in or close to the Sahara desert, and most of their populations are Muslim. Those in the centre and east of Africa are more heterogeneous, both in size and scientific output. Cameroon dominates in research (see Figure 2), but the Democratic Republic of Congo leads in both population and wealth, although it is classed as Low Income. Equatorial Guinea and Comoros are tiny countries with little research output, but the former, and Gabon, are classed as Upper Middle Income countries because of their mineral wealth.

Figure 2. Plot of research output (all subject areas, articles and reviews, integer counts) in 2019-21 against the Gross Domestic Product in 2018 of 18 Francophone African countries; log-log scales. For ISO codes, see Table 1.

We looked at the research outputs of the 20 Francophone countries in the last three years (2019-21), and compared them with the countries' wealth, as shown by their gross domestic product (GDP) in 2018, expressed in billion US dollars (data from the International Monetary Fund, IMF). The results are shown in Figure 2. There is a moderate positive correlation, but it is less than for European countries in cancer research (see Begum et al., 2018), which is typical for high-income countries. Equatorial Guinea (GQ) has an output far less than that expected from the least-squares trend-line (less than 6%), and that of Chad (TD) is only one third of the amount expected. On the other hand, Benin (BJ) and Cameroon (CM) both publish more than three times the expected amounts. These data are all *integer* counts, and are therefore magnified over fractional counts, which give a better indication of a country's performance. The amount of international collaboration is likely to be higher for countries with low outputs, such as Equatorial Guinea and Chad, than for ones such as Cameroon; this would make the above results more extreme.

We next looked at the distribution of the Francophone African research output between the major fields (see Table 2), and compared this with that of France, a high-income country that might be regarded as a major potential destination for emigrating Francophone scientists. This is shown in Figure 3. The major fields are ranked by the outputs of the African countries. Note that the percentages sum to more than 100% as many papers are classed by the WoS into more than one subject category, which we may have put into different major fields. In Figure 2, medicine is by far the major field of greatest interest to the Francophone African researchers, with 43% of total output, compared with just 30% in France. On the other hand, France does relatively much more work on the physical sciences such as chemistry, engineering, physics, and materials science. We might therefore expect that those Francophone African researchers who are emigrating to France might be relatively concentrated in these subject areas.

Figure 3. The distribution of research papers, 2009-21, from 18 Francophone African countries in 13 major fields (for codes, see Table 2), compared with the similar distribution for France.

Since our study is examining the situation in the individual countries, we also determined the numbers of papers from each country in each major field in 2009-21. These were compared with the average relative specialisation for the whole group, so as to show the differences between the countries. The results are shown in Table 3. Cameroon (CM), by far the largest country scientifically (see Figure 2), has an output fairly similar to that of France, with relatively large numbers of papers in the physical sciences, and correspondingly fewer in medicine, biology and agriculture. Benin (BJ) concentrates on agriculture, and Côte d'Ivoire (CI) on humanities. The Democratic Republic of Congo (CD), the largest of the 20 countries in terms of both population (Table 1) and GDP (Figure 1), concentrates on medical research, as does the other Congo (CG), and Guinea (GN). Madagascar (MG), which as a large island has many endemic species of fauna and flora, has focussed heavily on biology. However, the relative specialisations of the seven countries at the foot of the table, each with a total of fewer than 1000 papers, are not statistically significant.

We turn now to the main results of the paper, namely the locations of the researchers with names characteristic of each of the 20 Francophone African countries, which are shown in Table 4. The right-hand column, labelled Avg or average, takes account of the populations of the different countries. Overall, rather more than half of the Francophone African researchers

in the north and west countries have emigrated, see Figure 4, but for the central and east countries, fewer than half have done so.

Table 3. The relative specialisation of 20 Francophone African countries (for ISO codes, see Table 1) on 13 major scientific fields (for codes see Table 2) in 2009-21 (integer counts). Ratios greater than $\sqrt{2}$ (1.414) are shown in bold type; those below $1/\sqrt{2}$ (0.707) are shown in *italic type*.

<i>ISO</i>	<i>MEDI</i>	<i>GEOG</i>	<i>BIOL</i>	<i>AGRI</i>	<i>CHEM</i>	<i>ENGR</i>	<i>SOCI</i>	<i>MULT</i>	<i>PHYS</i>	<i>MATH</i>	<i>MATE</i>	<i>INFO</i>	<i>HUMA</i>
CM	0.85	0.90	0.77	0.89	1.61	1.45	1.04	0.96	2.04	1.49	1.56	1.48	1.21
SN	1.03	0.96	0.94	0.83	0.74	0.87	1.14	0.97	0.81	1.63	0.87	1.08	0.90
BF	1.23	0.95	0.88	1.03	<i>0.57</i>	0.90	0.84	1.07	<i>0.40</i>	0.92	<i>0.60</i>	<i>0.50</i>	<i>0.32</i>
BJ	0.83	1.12	1.07	1.86	<i>0.50</i>	0.77	0.74	0.91	1.36	0.93	<i>0.46</i>	0.79	<i>0.40</i>
CI	0.99	0.98	1.00	1.09	1.17	0.89	1.07	0.94	<i>0.47</i>	<i>0.68</i>	1.15	1.17	1.68
CD	1.34	1.02	0.91	0.75	0.75	<i>0.65</i>	0.89	1.12	<i>0.27</i>	<i>0.14</i>	<i>0.62</i>	<i>0.37</i>	1.22
MG	0.74	1.41	1.89	1.28	0.96	<i>0.53</i>	<i>0.64</i>	1.28	<i>0.39</i>	<i>0.22</i>	<i>0.30</i>	<i>0.24</i>	<i>0.41</i>
ML	1.30	0.81	1.07	1.26	<i>0.45</i>	0.73	0.81	1.25	<i>0.09</i>	<i>0.36</i>	<i>0.39</i>	0.78	<i>0.64</i>
GA	1.19	0.95	1.40	<i>0.58</i>	0.76	<i>0.54</i>	<i>0.55</i>	1.68	<i>0.45</i>	<i>0.64</i>	<i>0.53</i>	<i>0.30</i>	0.91
CG	1.42	0.82	1.17	<i>0.62</i>	<i>0.37</i>	<i>0.27</i>	<i>0.52</i>	1.01	<i>0.54</i>	<i>0.66</i>	<i>0.25</i>	<i>0.32</i>	<i>0.36</i>
NE	0.92	1.45	0.92	1.41	0.47	1.02	0.83	0.88	<i>0.45</i>	<i>0.71</i>	1.09	0.83	0.73
TG	1.17	0.80	0.87	0.96	<i>0.51</i>	0.97	1.29	0.76	0.79	<i>0.41</i>	1.77	<i>0.16</i>	0.78
GN	1.62	<i>0.50</i>	1.06	<i>0.61</i>	<i>0.54</i>	<i>0.41</i>	<i>0.55</i>	1.03	<i>0.07</i>	<i>0.29</i>	<i>0.11</i>	<i>0.31</i>	<i>0.71</i>
BI	0.97	1.06	<i>0.69</i>	1.32	0.77	1.28	1.67	0.78	0.83	<i>0.25</i>	1.05	2.05	1.40
CF	1.27	0.80	1.27	<i>0.38</i>	<i>0.60</i>	<i>0.54</i>	<i>0.60</i>	1.67	<i>0.64</i>	0.85	1.24	<i>0.48</i>	<i>0.55</i>
MR	0.92	1.35	1.05	<i>0.66</i>	1.28	1.20	<i>0.40</i>	<i>0.66</i>	1.24	1.50	1.01	1.62	<i>0.37</i>
TD	1.17	0.99	<i>0.65</i>	<i>0.53</i>	<i>0.36</i>	1.03	1.21	1.29	0.88	1.28	0.96	1.37	1.75
DJ	0.88	1.74	1.02	<i>0.63</i>	0.99	1.81	<i>0.29</i>	0.92	0.86	<i>0.13</i>	1.71	<i>0.00</i>	<i>0.47</i>
KM	0.81	1.66	1.69	0.77	1.06	<i>0.58</i>	0.81	0.80	<i>0.46</i>	<i>0.41</i>	<i>0.46</i>	<i>0.00</i>	0.75
GQ	1.14	<i>0.65</i>	1.65	<i>0.30</i>	0.80	<i>0.00</i>	<i>0.44</i>	2.86	<i>0.00</i>	<i>0.00</i>	<i>0.00</i>	<i>0.00</i>	1.88

Figure 4. Average percentages of locations of researchers with names characteristic of ten north and west and ten central and east Francophone African countries in First and Second time periods.

The difference between 2009-11 and 2019-21 is quite small for the N & W countries, but larger for the C & E ones. There has been a noticeable reduction in the numbers from both groups going to Europe, of about 3% of the total. Almost all of this reduction was in researchers moving to France; the percentages going to other western European countries were almost unchanged. Instead the researchers have increasingly gone to other African countries, and a few have gone to Asia, more from the N & W countries.

Table 4 shows that four of the north and west countries suffered a greater "brain drain" than the other six, namely Chad (TD), Mauritania (MR), Senegal (SN), and Côte d'Ivoire (CI). Many of the researchers from Niger (NE) and Mauritania went to other African countries, and for most source countries this has increased with time. However, for most of the ten countries (but not Chad), emigration to Europe has decreased, especially to France. For the central and eastern countries, the exodus was lower, but still more than half in Djibouti (DJ) and Benin (BJ), and just 50% in the Democratic Republic of Congo (CD). It was noticeably lower in western Europe, perhaps because of physical distance, but much greater to South Africa (2.6% compared with 0.7% from the northern and western countries), for the same reason.

The most popular sub-Saharan African destination overall was South Africa, with 20% of those moving to other countries within the continent, followed by Nigeria (8.3%) and Cameroon (6.4%). Of those who went to Asia, the most popular country was mainland China (24%), followed by Japan (19%) and India (12%). Within Europe, other than France which took 50% of the African emigrants, the most popular host countries were Germany (12.5%), Belgium (9.9%), and the UK (8.2%). However, researchers from the Democratic Republic of Congo preferred to go to Belgium (8.4% of all emigrants), the former colonial power, rather than France (5.4%). Within North America, 26% of the African emigrants went to Canada in 2009-11, and 31% in 2019-21. These percentages are much higher than the ratio of populations, or of research outputs, and may be accounted for by Francophone Quebec province, or a more welcoming immigration policy in Canada for African researchers.

Table 4. The present location (percentages) of the researchers with names characteristic of each of the ten northern and western Francophone African countries (upper table) and ten central and eastern countries (lower table) (for ISO codes, see Table 1) in the two periods, 1st = 2009-11 and 2nd = 2019-21. *W Eur* = western Europe; *N Am* = North America (Canada + USA). *Avg* = average, based on population of countries

<i>N & W</i>	<i>Time</i>	<i>BF</i>	<i>BJ</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>GN</i>	<i>ML</i>	<i>MR</i>	<i>NE</i>	<i>SN</i>	<i>TD</i>	<i>TG</i>	<i>Avg</i>
Own	1st	64.0	65.7	28.4	55.6	50.4	23.2	40.6	26.0	0.0	62.9	41.5
	2nd	60.7	61.2	30.5	51.1	47.1	24.0	43.5	27.5	22.6	65.1	43.1
Africa	1st	7.9	11.4	10.7	0.0	7.3	27.5	24.0	7.5	0.0	12.6	10.0
	2nd	12.8	11.7	10.4	14.9	16.5	24.0	31.2	13.2	19.4	16.9	16.6
Asia	1st	2.1	2.3	10.7	11.1	6.5	5.8	7.3	8.2	25.0	1.1	8.4
	2nd	2.7	3.6	9.6	8.5	6.9	14.9	12.4	10.2	6.5	1.8	7.7
W Eur	1st	20.2	14.6	29.5	33.3	23.6	33.3	19.8	34.3	25.0	16.0	24.9
	2nd	15.5	16.0	29.9	23.4	16.8	29.1	8.8	28.9	41.9	9.5	21.8
France	1st	12.8	9.7	13.0	22.2	16.3	15.9	14.6	17.3	0.0	10.9	13.3
	2nd	8.5	9.2	13.8	14.9	11.0	16.6	5.3	15.0	12.9	6.0	11.1
N Am	1st	4.5	4.9	16.2	0.0	10.6	10.1	6.3	18.3	25.0	6.3	10.7
	2nd	7.2	5.9	15.1	2.1	9.3	6.9	2.9	14.3	9.7	6.0	8.6
Other	1st	1.2	1.1	4.5	0.0	1.6	0.0	2.1	5.8	25.0	1.1	4.5
	2nd	1.2	1.6	4.6	0.0	3.4	1.1	1.2	5.8	0.0	0.7	2.3

<i>C & E</i>	<i>Time</i>	<i>BI</i>	<i>CD</i>	<i>CF</i>	<i>CG</i>	<i>CM</i>	<i>DJ</i>	<i>GA</i>	<i>GQ</i>	<i>KM</i>	<i>MG</i>	<i>Avg</i>
Own	1st	43.2	48.0	96.8	35.7	66.2	36.0	61.1	10.0	28.6	65.0	53.1
	2nd	33.0	51.0	91.9	61.0	71.0	21.0	86.0	50.0	76.7	66.0	65.4
Africa	1st	11.4	13.9	0.0	14.3	5.2	21.0	4.6	0.0	42.9	2.0	9.8
	2nd	32.5	18.0	2.7	13.5	6.5	24.0	3.8	0.0	0.0	2.5	9.6
Asia	1st	2.3	6.1	0.0	5.0	3.4	14.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	2.1
	2nd	5.0	7.2	0.0	5.4	3.7	32.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.4	3.2
W Eur	1st	29.5	16.0	3.2	32.1	15.0	21.0	26.9	0.0	28.6	25.0	18.6
	2nd	14.5	9.9	2.7	12.5	9.6	21.0	7.7	50.0	23.3	23.0	15.6
France	1st	6.8	3.5	3.2	25.0	5.5	21.0	22.2	0.0	28.6	20.0	11.8
	2nd	3.0	2.4	2.7	7.4	2.5	15.0	4.5	0.0	16.7	16.0	5.4
N Am	1st	13.6	13.0	0.0	10.0	9.0	7.1	7.4	0.0	0.0	6.0	6.3
	2nd	14.0	11.0	0.0	5.3	8.0	0.0	2.4	0.0	0.0	5.1	4.8
Other	1st	0.0	2.8	0.0	2.9	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.6
	2nd	1.0	2.4	2.7	2.3	1.3	2.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	1.3

The next two tables show the pattern of emigration to different continents by researchers from the two sets of ten countries. Table 5 shows the percentages of people in the different major fields and continents. The distribution of the selected researchers by major field mirrors very closely ($r^2 = 0.963$) that of the African research outputs (Figure 3), showing that our name samples were reasonably representative. Medicine was by far the most popular field for both sets of researchers, followed at some distance by geographical and agricultural sciences.

Table 6 shows the ratio of these numbers to those that would be expected if people in every field expressed no preference for where to go (or whether to stay at home) compared with those

of the two Francophone African populations. There was a modest tendency for medical and agricultural researchers to remain at home, with the biologists, but chemists, engineers, materials and information scientists were more likely to go abroad, especially the latter. The chemists went primarily to Asia, and secondarily to Europe, as did the engineers, who also favoured Oceania, mainly Australia. The Information scientists went mainly to Asia and western Europe, and the materials scientists to Asia and also to other African countries. The social scientists from the northern and western countries went mainly to North America, but those from the other countries preferred Asia and Latin America. The physicists emigrated primarily to western Europe; those from the N & W countries preferred Latin America and Oceania while those from the C & E countries liked Asia.

Table 5. The destination continents of researchers from ten northern and western Francophone African countries (upper table) and ten central and eastern countries (lower table) according to their major field (for codes, see Table 2). Figures are percentages, weighted by population of the individual countries. *OWN* = own country; *EUR* = Western Europe; *AFR* = other African country; *NAM* = North America (Canada + USA); *ASI* = Asia; *LAC* = Latin America + Caribbean; *EEU* = Eastern Europe; *OCE* = Oceania Note: Percentages of continents sum to 100% but percentages of fields sum to 126% because of double-counting.

<i>N & W</i>	<i>OWN</i>	<i>EUR</i>	<i>AFR</i>	<i>NAM</i>	<i>ASI</i>	<i>LAC</i>	<i>EEU</i>	<i>OCE</i>	<i>Total</i>
MEDI	26.58	9.99	7.84	3.97	2.06	0.60	0.32	0.12	51.48
AGRI	6.43	1.55	1.50	0.43	0.83	0.42	0.06	0.01	11.23
GEOG	4.83	2.64	2.00	0.59	0.60	0.05	0.12	0.06	10.9
ENGR	1.83	3.57	1.69	1.77	1.40	0.09	0.09	0.14	10.6
CHEM	2.74	3.93	1.31	0.90	1.30	0.06	0.21	0.05	10.5
BIOL	4.05	1.32	0.97	0.78	0.77	0.09	0.03	0.03	8.03
MULT	3.15	1.47	1.69	0.39	0.40	0.01	0.05	0.01	7.17
SOCI	1.42	1.50	0.58	1.48	0.54	0.11	0.09	0.08	5.80
PHYS	0.68	1.14	0.23	0.52	0.31	0.05	0.03	0.03	2.99
MATH	1.24	0.64	0.36	0.11	0.12	0.04	0.04	0.04	2.59
INFO	0.25	0.87	0.19	0.20	0.61	0.00	0.00	0.01	2.13
MATE	0.24	0.40	0.34	0.08	0.51	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.57
HUMA	0.22	0.22	0.15	0.09	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.73
Total	42.69	23.25	14.99	8.99	7.57	1.22	0.84	0.47	

<i>C & E</i>	<i>OWN</i>	<i>EUR</i>	<i>AFR</i>	<i>NAM</i>	<i>ASI</i>	<i>EEU</i>	<i>LAC</i>	<i>OCE</i>	<i>Total</i>
MEDI	36.26	7.13	7.25	5.25	1.57	0.42	0.31	0.11	58.29
GEOG	9.86	1.88	1.92	0.82	1.10	0.12	0.09	0.01	15.80
AGRI	7.64	1.59	1.38	0.45	0.64	0.09	0.07	0.03	11.89
CHEM	3.50	2.34	1.11	1.44	1.16	0.15	0.07	0.10	9.87
BIOL	5.83	1.29	1.04	0.73	0.30	0.19	0.07	0.05	9.49
MULT	4.51	0.83	0.99	0.54	0.14	0.09	0.01	0.02	7.13
SOCI	2.01	1.06	1.29	1.13	0.38	0.10	0.01	0.07	6.05
ENGR	1.53	1.55	0.81	0.68	1.13	0.06	0.09	0.03	5.89
PHYS	0.98	0.62	0.34	0.13	0.22	0.02	0.00	0.00	2.32
MATH	1.00	0.24	0.38	0.23	0.21	0.01	0.00	0.00	2.07
INFO	0.40	0.55	0.28	0.27	0.39	0.02	0.02	0.01	1.93
MATE	0.68	0.28	0.43	0.17	0.18	0.05	0.00	0.04	1.82
HUMA	0.32	0.15	0.34	0.12	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.94
Total	55.82	14.60	13.16	8.96	5.56	0.98	0.56	0.35	

Table 6. Ratios of observed to expected numbers of researchers from ten northern and western Francophone African countries (upper table) and ten central and eastern countries (lower table) who went to different continents, and worked in different major fields (for codes, see Table 2).

For continent codes, see caption to Table 5. Ratios greater than $\sqrt{2}$ (1.414) are shown in bold type; those below $1/\sqrt{2}$ (0.707) are shown in italic type and those below 0.5 are shown in small italic type

<i>N & W</i>	<i>OWN</i>	<i>EUR</i>	<i>AFR</i>	<i>NAM</i>	<i>ASI</i>	<i>LAC</i>	<i>EEU</i>	<i>OCE</i>
MEDI	1.15	0.83	1.02	0.97	0.67	1.12	0.77	0.49
AGRI	1.33	0.65	1.12	0.41	0.74	1.14	0.62	0.63
GEOG	1.05	0.96	1.19	0.66	0.96	0.38	1.64	0.70
CHEM	0.54	1.52	0.92	1.10	1.86	1.05	2.58	1.46
BIOL	1.16	0.95	0.77	0.92	0.89	0.80	0.35	0.44
ENGR	0.47	1.52	0.87	1.66	1.79	0.91	1.19	2.02
SOCI	0.62	1.17	0.61	2.24	1.34	1.62	1.51	3.85
MULT	1.11	0.88	1.42	0.78	0.54	0.00	0.53	0.67
PHYS	0.75	1.36	0.66	1.16	1.30	2.46	1.34	3.41
MATH	1.19	0.90	1.02	0.68	0.56	1.51	0.55	1.40
INFO	0.43	1.40	0.91	1.67	2.69	0.00	0.00	1.91
MATE	0.44	1.71	1.40	0.37	2.75	0.00	0.00	0.00
HUMA	0.49	1.60	0.88	2.10	0.97	1.74	0.00	0.00

C & E	<i>OWN</i>	<i>EUR</i>	<i>AFR</i>	<i>NAM</i>	<i>ASI</i>	<i>LAC</i>	<i>EEU</i>	<i>OCE</i>
MEDI	1.11	0.84	0.95	1.00	0.48	0.94	0.73	0.55
GEOG	1.12	0.81	0.92	0.58	1.26	1.02	0.78	0.11
AGRI	1.15	0.91	0.88	0.42	0.97	1.05	0.80	0.74
CHEM	0.64	1.63	0.85	1.63	2.12	1.18	1.58	2.78
BIOL	1.10	0.93	0.83	0.86	0.57	1.29	2.01	1.49
MULT	1.13	0.80	1.06	0.84	0.35	0.32	1.34	0.87
ENGR	0.60	1.20	1.62	2.09	1.12	0.37	1.63	3.23
SOCI	0.47	1.80	1.05	1.29	3.45	2.83	1.03	1.52
PHYS	0.76	1.83	1.11	0.63	1.72	0.24	0.98	0.00
MATH	0.86	0.81	1.39	1.25	1.79	0.26	0.30	0.42
INFO	0.37	1.93	1.09	1.59	3.65	1.76	0.83	1.86
MATE	0.67	1.06	1.78	1.02	1.78	0.00	2.61	5.52
HUMA	0.61	1.07	2.78	1.48	0.00	0.58	0.00	0.00

The sex of the researchers, as the ratio of females to (males + females), is shown in Table 7 for the different continental destinations and major fields. Columns and rows for these two parameters have been sorted by this percentage, but for some cells there were few researchers. It is striking that the lowest percentage of females overall is among those who stayed in their own country (22%), followed by those who went to another African country or one in Asia (23% and 24%). Those who went to Europe fared somewhat better (31%), but not as well as the (relatively small) numbers who travelled to Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC, 29%) or Oceania (31%). For those who remained at home, the percentage of females was highest in medicine (26%), and as expected this percentage was much lower for materials science, mathematics, engineering, and physics. However, overall, female social scientists (30%) and chemists (27%) fared best because more of them went abroad to North America and Europe.

There were also some differences between the countries overall in terms of the presence of females among all their researchers. Of those countries with at least 100 named researchers, Madagascar had much the highest percentage of females (51%), followed at some distance by Côte d'Ivoire and Gabon (29%). Mali (17%) and Benin (18%) had the lowest percentages of females. However, these values are based only on researchers with selected surnames, and may not be representative of all researchers in these countries.

The ranking of the countries by percentage of females for papers from the named researchers working in their home countries (OWN) agrees fairly well with the sex ratio for all papers from the 11 countries with > 100 researchers in the six years (2009-11 and 2019-21); the r^2 value was 0.89. The female percentage for the named researchers in the ten north and west countries increased from 22.9% in 2009-11 to 23.7% in 2019-21, and that in the ten central and eastern countries from 25.9% to 27.8%. These increases are very modest, and the percentages are well below the world averages, and far below the par value of 50%, except for Madagascar.

Table 7. The percentages of female researchers (of those who could be sexed) from ten northern and western Francophone African countries (upper table) and ten central and eastern countries (lower table), 2009-11 and 2019-21, who work in different major fields (rows; for codes see Table 2) and are in different continental regions (columns).

<i>% F, N&W</i>	<i>NAM</i>	<i>EUR</i>	<i>LAC</i>	<i>OCE</i>	<i>EEU</i>	<i>AFR</i>	<i>ASI</i>	<i>OWN</i>	<i>Total</i>
HUMA	40	67				0	0	20	38.9
SOCI	42	27	0	100	0	21	28	17	28.4
MEDI	45	33	42	25	33	25	20	23	28.2
CHEM	37	31	33	0	22	24	23	14	26.4
MULT	27	23	0		0	22	14	28	25.0
BIOL	34	37	40	0	0	9	42	16	24.2
INFO	29	37				13	20	9	24.2
PHYS	45	21	0		0	20	31	7	19.8
GEOG	13	28	50		29	31	14	10	17.9
AGRI	20	19	0	0	0	10	10	17	16.1
MATE	33	13				0	33	0	15.6
ENGR	6	19	0	0	0	18	12	13	13.7
MATH	25	0	0	0	0	8	50	2	5.2
Total N & W	34	28	26	24	22	21	21	18	23.4
<hr/>									
<i>% F, C&E</i>	<i>OCE</i>	<i>EUR</i>	<i>LAC</i>	<i>EEU</i>	<i>NAM</i>	<i>ASI</i>	<i>OWN</i>	<i>AFR</i>	<i>Total</i>
BIOL		47	0	0	33	40	28	15	30.8
MEDI	44	38	25	28	35	32	29	23	30.7
SOCI	0	26	67	83	30	47	25	36	30.6
CHEM	25	35	50	18	34	21	21	33	28.4
MULT	75	30	100	0	25	22	28	21	27.6
AGRI	60	31	50	50	17	32	23	21	25.1
HUMA		43	0		0		22	27	25.0
GEOG	33	31	25	50	29	23	22	26	24.4
MATE	0	39		33	10	25	12	40	24.2
INFO		29	0	0	17	17	18	29	21.0
ENGR	25	22	25	25	35	16	12	25	20.2
PHYS		24	0	33	25	25	14	25	19.4
MATH	0	19		0	16	22	5	11	10.4
Total C & E	38	34	32	31	31	26	24	24	27.3

Our last analysis was of the amount of collaboration between those Francophone African researchers who had gone abroad and ones in their former home country. Table 8 gives the results for five relatively productive countries, scientifically, and for three less productive ones. All of the emigrant cohorts published papers in collaboration with their heritage or “home” countries, except for Chad. The expected numbers, based on their presence in world research in the six years, 2009-11 and 2019-21, are given in the seventh column of the table, and, other than for Chad, the ratios in the eighth column are very much greater than unity showing that the emigrant researchers maintain a very strong preference for continuing to work with their heritage countries.

Table 8. The tendency of emigrant researchers from eight Francophone sub-Saharan African countries to publish papers in collaboration with their “own” or heritage country, 2009-11 and 2019-21.

<i>Country</i>	<i>ISO</i>	<i>% world</i>	<i>Emigrants</i>	<i>Output</i>	<i>Own country</i>	<i>Expected</i>	<i>Ratio</i>
Cameroon	CM	0.0692	997	4100	245	2.84	86
Senegal	SN	0.0287	519	3265	43	0.937	46
Burkina Faso	BF	0.0245	151	461	41	0.113	363
Côte d’Ivoire	CI	0.0229	460	3695	107	0.846	126
Benin	BJ	0.0224	260	805	68	0.180	377
Burundi	BI	0.0030	101	307	6	0.0092	651
Mauritania	MR	0.0024	110	394	3	0.0095	317
Chad	TD	0.0022	17	128	0	0.0028	0

Discussion and conclusions

We were initially somewhat surprised that our methodology of identification of researchers from individual African countries on the basis of their surnames worked, *i.e.*, that there were many surnames that very largely derived from just one country in Africa. However, in order to carry out the analysis, we frequently had to discard many names. For example, although we retained 97 Senegalese surnames, we had to discard 221 which occur in the country, but more frequently elsewhere. On the other hand, Malagasy names (from Madagascar) are so particular to that country that we retained 736 and only discarded three.

Although these African countries share a French colonial heritage (except for the Democratic Republic of Congo, which was Belgian), they differ greatly in their scientific outputs and the tendency of their researchers to emigrate. For many of them, their loss of scientists has been very serious, although a small but increasing number have gone to other African countries. Those countries that have suffered the most from emigration are experiencing political instability and violence, which are not conducive to research. Another factor contributing to the African brain drain is the policy of many destination countries, in Europe and north America, to lower the entry barriers to potential emigrants from Africa and elsewhere for those who are highly educated and can bring much-needed skills. However, there are two scientific fields in which researchers are less likely to emigrate. In medicine, there are opportunities in most countries for researchers also to practise their profession in the private sector, and so achieve a decent standard of living. They may also struggle to gain the qualifications necessary to practise medicine in their prospective host country. In many other scientific fields, a PhD suffices to show competence in research. In agriculture, the experience and skills of researchers in an African country are much less transferable to other continents, so these researchers’ job opportunities abroad will be less. This is borne out by the results shown in Table 6, where the agricultural and medical researchers are seen to be the most likely to remain at home.

We have divided up the 20 countries into two groups. The north and west countries not only differ in their physical characteristics, most of them being in or near the Sahara desert, but also in their relative proximity to Europe. This is likely to be a factor in their greater tendency to emigrate there, and also to north America, seen in Table 4. However, the percentages who have gone to these regions have relatively declined. This probably reflects the increasing hostility of most European governments, and the USA, to emigrants from Africa, whether they are desperate refugees from violence or researchers with PhDs. There does not seem to be a

corresponding reluctance from Asian countries, especially China, to accept African researchers, and 13 of the 20 countries have seen an increase in the percentage of researchers working there, despite the difficulties of language and culture that they would have encountered.

Some individual African countries seem to have been quite successful in retaining their researchers, and there are some that have provided a fair opportunity for females to pursue careers in research. The data from Capuano & Marfouk (2013), Table 2 and Figure 3, suggest that the Francophone countries suffer much less from emigration than several Anglophone ones such as Ghana and Kenya. This could be because their researchers are likely to be less fluent in English. We endeavoured to find country characteristics that might explain these variations, seen in Tables 4 (for emigration) and 7 (for female participation). An independent source of information on the 54 African countries is the Africa Country Benchmark Report. This is published every few years by In On Africa (IOA), a multi-national consultancy company headquartered in South Africa (<https://www.inonafrika.com>). The 2016 edition lists the characteristics of the countries under four headings: politics, economy, business, and society. Each of these is sub-divided into four indexes with weights adding to 25% so as to give a comprehensive ranking of the countries. For the purposes of comparison with the research situation in each country, shown by three parameters:

- Ratio of observed research output to that expected from the GDP trend-line (R)
- Percentage of female researchers (F %)
- Percentage of named researchers who remain in their home country (H %)

we compiled the composite indicators for politics, the economy, and society for the 20 Francophone sub-Saharan countries considered in this study. We subtracted all the values (which ranged from 1 to 54) from 60 so that they might correlate positively with the three parameters.

There were therefore nine potential correlations. However only three were positive. These were the effect of society on F % ($r^2 = 0.105$), and of both politics and the economy on the research ratio (R; $r^2 = 0.24$). Madagascar (MG) provides far more opportunities for females than expected, but Mauritania (MR) and Djibouti (DJ) barely half as much. None of the indicators had any effect on the percentage of researchers who remained at home (H %).

There has recently been published (Miliband et al., 2023) an *Atlas of Impunity*, which ranks almost every country on the basis of published indicators of “the exercise of power without accountability”. We thought that this might have an influence on the willingness (or sometimes the necessity) of African researchers to leave their home country. We compared this index, which goes from zero (the least impunity, e.g. Finland) to five (the worst e.g., Afghanistan), but found zero correlation with the percentage of researchers remaining in their home country (Table 4, 2nd period) for the 20 countries in our study. So it does not seem possible to relate the propensity of African researchers to emigrate to any of the available statistics on the countries’ situation or governance.

However, the departure of highly trained personnel from Africa is not inevitable. A survey by Hutch et al. (2017) of training centres in east Africa revealed that well over 80% of surgeons who they trained were still practising in Africa, although a few were in neighbouring countries. This also occurred in west Africa (Gyedu, 2017) and contrasted with the experience of surgeons sent abroad for their training who mostly failed to return home.

It became clear that the researchers who emigrated maintained research links with their former home countries at a level that was many times higher than predicted if they had not expressed

any preference, see Table 8. Although we only explored the situation in eight countries, the results were consistent (except for Chad). This suggests that the loss of an African country's researchers will not be an entirely negative experience, as it may lead to more collaboration with good scientists in more highly developed nations and provide a means for the transfer of knowledge and access to advanced equipment. There may also be a transfer of funds, as remittances from emigrants back to their former home countries in Africa are often a major source of improvements in democracy (Williams, 2017), in education and health (Amega, 2018), in human development (Sahoo & Sethi, 2020), and in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs; Akanle et al., 2022).

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